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FEMaLe**

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1. Let's preface FEMaLe internal dissemination

1.1 The context of the rational and relational lexica

With results, efficiency and performance in mind Julia Unwin produced a report that, in matters of policy making, emphasized the importance of remembering that fact that we create results, are efficient and perform with our colleagues, employees and co-workers. In other words, together. What we want in FEMaLe is to motivate you to *want* to do that rather than *having* to.

In Section 1 we will introduce you to a positive and people-focused mindset with which we believe we can achieve even more, together. In FEMaLe, let's remember that most basic of truths can easily be forgotten in pursuits of progress – that we can and will only succeed together.

Let's look at Julia Unwin's lexica and consider which words from both lexica we can actively use in FEMaLe to inspire the communicative, collaborative and co-creation aspect of all our deliverables.

Let's proceed to the next page to make the above words more tangible by introducing a FEMaLe story.

Illustration 1: From Kindness, emotions and human relationships. Carnegie Report.

1.2 The human part of the FEMaLe equation

Within FEMaLe, do our everyday actions help us come closer to reducing the number of people with undiagnosed and/or untreated endometriosis?

Can we collectively make the FEMaLe machine operate such that we reach our proposed numbers?
Can we? Sure. But do you remember why we do so in the first place?

As this document is intended to be a guiding repository you can consult if you're unclear about which tools to use to achieve our collective goals – but also if you're unclear as to why we want to accomplish said goals.

Let's exemplify by discovering this writer's 'why' by using tool 10, Storytelling:

Ten years ago, a couple was having the time of their lives! They were in their late thirties and had just bought a newly built house in the suburbs a few minutes outside the capital. Their careers had steadily been getting better so money afforded them whatever their hearts desired in a heartbeat. Their house had designer furniture in every room and original paintings on the walls, life had indeed been good to them. What more could they ask for?

For years, while they both progressed with their careers and enjoyed life, they also wanted to enrich their lives with children. For years they had tried and for years their attempts were unsuccessful.

The couple decided to go to the doctor to help determine why their yearlong attempts at getting pregnant didn't bear any fruit. Like the couple, the doctor was puzzled that nothing had come of their continuous effort at having children, but the doctor, like the couple, never could pinpoint the reason for the infertility.

To this day, ten years later, they still have not conceived a child, as she was afflicted by endometriosis and her particular kind had rendered her forever incapable of having children.

Years trying to create that which they could never have, she felt betrayed by her body and by an insufficient healthcare system. She is and forever will be unable to bring life into this world, her lifelong dream, a dream that had turned into a living nightmare.

With a deep frustration of how long it currently takes to diagnose endometriosis FEMaLe exists to now pave the way to empower the powerless, infuse the hopeless with hope... this, our fellow *FEMaLers*, is our story being written in real-time, it will be the legacy of FEMaLe, it is our purpose imbued in each of us. Millions with endometriosis depend on us.

The above story is this writer's personal motivation for being a part of FEMaLe. It makes him want to help the project succeed with every thought, with every task he performs and with every interaction he has with any of you. He wants to help reduce the absurdly large number of women that are afflicted with debilitating endometriosis.

Have you discovered your 'why' yet?
Don't worry, let's discover it together!

1.3 A slogan and an analysis

In an attempt to make the previous pages more tangible we have created the following slogan.

'Let's...'

...is a casual and slightly disguised way of suggesting that we should do, propose or break the ice on something together, let us. Like a severely under diagnosed and taboo topic, let's say.

...has a forthcoming curious, innocent tone to it as well as an almost irresistible connotation that actively urges us to get involved and explore.

In the pursuit of a short and simple yet encouraging verb we settled on the one with the most positive connotations we could think of. It is intended to be used on every level of communication within FEMaLe, from video communications to meetings, to emails, to tutorials - even document names. Everything.

We intend for every FEMaLer to become and breathe what 'Let's' stands for.

We will pursue this end by hosting workshops intended for every FEMaLer to find their own 'Let's' to underscore their personal affiliation, to underscore why they are invested in the project.

'make life better...'

...are generic, yet unquestionably words that anyone can relate to, all know them. They were chosen as they have a universal appeal and potentially have deep personal significance.

...is the active part of the slogan and as such, it will appear front and center along with the FEMaLe logo as an ever-present reminder of the potential and what we aim to achieve with FEMaLe.

...is a project-wide, team-wide or individual rallying cry for each FEMaLer to pursue and progress towards. It's the ever bright guiding star that will show the way.

1+1=?

With the Half Double framework to guide FEMaLe's choices of means to reach our goals, merged, the two parts of this slogan become something more. They become a virtue, a standard to uphold, a code by which to act.

#LetsMakeLifeBetter

Illustration 2: The FEMaLe logo with a proposed slogan

2. Let's explore internal dissemination

2.1 What is internal dissemination

Dissemination is the act of spreading news, information, ideas, etc. to a lot of people – internally within FEMaLe.

With Julia Unwin's two lexica in mind, and with the goal in mind to create a psychological safe haven, we also want dissemination to be the act of sharing and more specifically, *wanting* to share.

Project findings, acquired knowledge, accomplishments, sure. But let's also include and encourage sharing feelings, stories, ups and downs. In Section 2, tool 9 (employee branding) of this document we will go into greater detail about how we want to do that and what it can accomplish.

Internal communications are often thought of as top-down messaging, written by leaders for the consumption of employees. We promote two-way communication around what's happening in FEMaLe.

People want to feel like their input matters and their voices are being heard and creating venues for them to do so is going to do wonders for building engagement and morale, which will lead to more generally satisfied FEMaLers.

2.2 How to use this handbook

This document is intended to be a guiding repository that you can consult if you're unclear about which tools to use to achieve our collective goals – but also if you're unclear as to why we want to accomplish said goals.

In section 1 you can be reminded why FEMaLe exists, in a more relational and less rational way.

In section 3 you can find the tools that enable us to accomplish our goals – together. Most of which are rational, few are relational as seen in the overview provided in the table of contents.

3. Let's explore the proposed FEMaLe internal dissemination toolbox

Section 3 gives an overview over dissemination tools intended to be used in FEMaLe in a prioritized fashion. The communication and dissemination strategy follows the half double framework in that its tools are chosen for their ability to synergistically create impact, encourage co-creation.

3.1 Correlate

Correlate³ is a Data-Driven Management Platform that provides a secure, easy and flexible solution to synthesize data and information through a non-intrusive, lightweight, high performance, cost-efficient, easy-to-use desktop and mobile friendly web app that connects multi-cloud services.

The focus of the Correlate platform is to make files easily accessible and findable and aid in the co-operation and co-creation of tasks and workflows, and as such, synergizes well with the FEMaLe Half Double framework.

In FEMaLe, we will use the Correlate platform to interlink and share all documents among all WP team members, where each Beneficiary can access, search for and co-produce materials real-time.

The shared documents will remain stored on the Beneficiaries personal cloud services (e.g., Google Drive, Dropbox, OneDrive). Keep in mind that Correlate links to files and does not upload files to the platform, FEMaLe Correlate.

How to use Correlate?

Here you will find a step-by-step guide and manual that teaches you how to use the platform.

When to use Correlate?

All partners should upload content onto Correlate immediately after delivery completion.

3.2 Frequent updates

Another impact focused cornerstone of the Half Double framework is frequent updates.

They will consist of monthly newsletters and briefs from all WPs with content in the form of relevant status updates, developments and progress - or personal stories from that month.

As a team partner you can choose to give an update in various ways:

- Does your update come in the form of written words, that's good!
- Does it go to the next level and come in the form of a video, that's inspirational!
- Not every FEMaLer in every team must do this every month, but let's encourage passionately sharing in an authentic manner.

Let's co-create transparency between FEMaLers by sharing our ups and downs, successes and failures and let's reach out to aid when we can.

All WP leaders need to update their Half Double visual sprint chart monthly

We have yet to define where to share these updates.

³ <https://www.correlate.com>

How to use frequent updates?

Frequent updates will rely on people's willingness to share, which is why EQuIP will get the ball rolling to give examples of how it can be done.

Updates will be posted and can be accessed on the FEMaLe Correlate platform. Videos should contain answers to questions yet to be defined. Stay tuned.

When to use frequent updates?

Weekly: all partners will record a short video, talking about what they have been doing, how is it going, any problem they ran into, how do you want to solve the problem, and do you need help from any partners?

3.3 Miro

With more work being done remotely, it's more important than ever for teams to be able to successfully synergize and actively co-create visually plan and perform together - simultaneously.

As an online visual collaboration platform for teamwork, this is where Miro⁴ comes in and becomes an essential tool to support the Half Double framework methodology.

Miro allows you and your team to create notes, designs and move things around - powerful synergistic possibilities when combined with a video communication tool such as Zoom, Teams or Meet to optimize coordination. It also comes with pre-built templates that can inspire as a starting place.

How to use Miro?

In order to use Miro, a profile must be created, which the Miro team has made very easy to do by [following these steps](#). The Miro Academy is filled with tutorials about every single tool within Miro.

When to use Miro?

Sprint planning:

All WP will use a sprint planning board in Miro. This will be used to create the same 'language' and an overview over partners plans to create synergy. Partners will then have an overview of what other partners are doing and are encouraged to offer assistance.

Progress updates:

All WP leaders need to update their Half Double visual Gantt chart monthly in Miro.

⁴ [Learn more about miro here](#)

3.4 Half Double visuals (in Miro)

Visual thinking is an integral part of the Half Double methodology. It is manifested in the way the concept is presented as a circle that shows how different principles, methods and tools are connected.

More specifically, the use of visuals is central to securing flow in projects. The methodology suggests that visuals may be used for prototyping, problem solving and facilitation of group sessions as well as for sprint planning, etc.

Particularly visual sprint planning has been highlighted as a tool which provides a quick overview making it easier to understand how each activity is linked to an overall idea. It supports teamwork coordination and idea improvement.

A Half Double Visual can in that way help to secure project workflow and progression.

In FEMaLe, we use the online visual co-creation collaboration platform for teamwork, Miro, as the software with which these Half Double Visuals are made.

How to use Half Double visuals?

Through tutorials and workshops created in D1.1 and D10.1, we are confident that before the end of 2021, all FEMaLers will use Miro actively to create Half Double Visuals. Templates exist that we can utilize.

When to use Half Double visuals?

We will tailor Half Double visuals to Miro usage.

3.5 FEMaLe visual identity & logo

The logo plays a central role in the project's visual identity. It aids recollection and recall, and it should be included in all internal communications between partners.

The logo developed is clear and communicates the main concepts of FEMaLe – a person connected with machines – a strong message of machine learning is communicated subconsciously.

With a continuous effort, over time the logo will also carry the values of FEMaLe within order to underscore not only what FEMaLe does, but also why, its synergistic effect will be imbued in the logo itself. Communicating visually is also aligned with the Half Double methodology to create impact.

Image 2.2.2.1.1: Color palette with RGB and CMYK instructions for usage

How to use the FEMaLe visual identity & logo?

Web Bay created guidelines for the use of the FEMaLe visual identity and logo in D9.1; Web Bay has also created templates to be used for various purposes - those templates will be shared soon.

When to use the FEMaLe visual identity & logo?

When you generate any kind of output it should:

- a) include the FEMaLe logo
- b) use the colors that Web Bay has specified (like in this document)

3.6 Video communication

Physical meetings are less frequent in the first half of 2021 due to Covid-19 and video communication tools are on the rise as a substitution. They are live video-based meetings between two or more people in different locations using video-enabled devices. As such it synergizes extremely well with our primary tool, Miro, to maximize our Half Double co-creation efforts whilst preserving the human interaction aspect of collaborating.

How to use video communication

FEMaLe uses three different video communication tools, Zoom, Meet and Teams.

If you need to brush up on your video communication skills, here are tutorials for each:

- Find [Zoom](#)⁵ tutorials
- Find [Meet](#)⁶ tutorials
- Find [Teams](#)⁷ tutorials

When to use video communication?

When a physical meeting is not possible, inconvenient, not free, not necessary, not possible to video record.

3.7 Doodle

Doodle⁸ is a tool that brings people together in mere moments and ends time consuming back-and-forth emails. This tool's impact can be felt almost instantly after you start utilizing it and as such belongs in our Half Double oriented toolbox.

⁵ [Learn about Zoom](#)

⁶ [Learn about Meet](#)

⁷ [Learn about Teams](#)

⁸ [Learn about Doodle](#)

Users are asked to determine the best time and date to meet.

The organizer then chooses the time that suits everyone and the meeting is booked in your calendar.

Meeting coordinators (administrators) receive email alerts for votes and comments.

Doodle interacts with various external calendar systems such as Google Calendar, Yahoo Calendar and Microsoft Outlook.

How to use Doodle?

Doodle has [created guides](#) to quickly get to grips with the software and start stopping time wasting.

When to use Doodle?

A month before an intended meeting, a doodle poll will be created; all partners have 2 weeks to vote. The WP and/or Task Leader will then find the date that suits every partner.

3.8 SurveyXact

As the name suggests SurveyXact⁹ is a questionnaire-based survey tool. The program makes it possible to create an online survey and invite participants very easily through e.g. e-mail. It's a user-friendly, simple and quick to use tool that creates a good overview of collected data, which in turn are easy to export. Getting started and utilizing the basics is easy to ensure the Half Double impact.

How to use SurveyXact?

The creators of SurveyXact have an [online handbook](#) that explains every feature.

In FEMaLe its intended use is to align expectation, measure satisfaction and pulse-check.

When to use SurveyXact?

SurveyXact will be used as a tool for project pulse checks.

A survey will be sent to the partners once a month.

⁹ [Learn about SurveyXact](#)

3.9 Infographics

An infographic is a collection of imagery, charts, and minimal text that gives an easy-to-understand overview of a topic and as such a perfect fit for the Half Double framework that emphasizes using visuals whenever possible due to lower cognitive load required to decode messages.

Let's encourage the use of infographics synergistically to support all communications internally to make complex information easily digestible, to:

- Reports
- Provide a quick overview of a topic
- Explain a complex process
- Display research findings or survey data
- Summarize a long blog post or report
- Compare and contrast multiple options
- Raise awareness about an issue or cause

How to use infographics?

EQuIP has a multimedia graphics designer, Peter Lübben, connected to and designated for FEMaLe. He will do his best to serve and assist partners create tailored infographics, so let's start co-creating!

When to use infographics?

Consult the list of bullet points above and book a meeting with Peter. Let's tend to your needs.

3.10 Employee branding

Employee branding is the process by which FEMaLers internalize the agreed upon desired FEMaLe project values and are motivated to project them to others.^{10,11,12} It's a prerequisite to unlock the highest degree of Half Double impact and the highest level of passionate synergy within FEMaLe.

That sounds like something we want, so let's explore how we identify what the FEMaLe values are!

Together, we make them take form as we progress through a planned series of co-creation FEMaLe value identification workshops.

FEMaLers who feel that they're being listened to are more likely to contribute with enhanced performance, so let's focus on co-creating an engagement strategy that's rooted in open communication that takes place in an open environment that makes every FEMaLer feel heard, informed, inspired, educated and wanting to contribute.

How to use employee branding?

From June to September, EQUIP (P3) will develop the initial guidelines and steps towards deploying employee branding in FEMaLe with the goal of becoming FEMaLers and with our co-created values!

It's going to be easier to live the values that you, each of you FEMaLers, have helped define, which will make your motivation more authentic and interactions more fruitful and synergistic.

When to use employee branding?

Employee branding is a continuous effort in alignment with the FEMaLe mindset and values found in section 0, so WP leaders will hold meetings with their team on a monthly basis to secure proper value alignment.

¹⁰ <https://www.reviewtrackers.com/blog/employee-branding/>

¹¹ <https://blog.vantagecircle.com/employee-branding/>

¹² https://sproutsocial-com.cdn.ampproject.org/v/s/sproutsocial.com/insights/internal-communications-guide/?amp&_js_v=0.1&usqp=mq331AQHKAFQArABIA%3D%3D#bestpractices

3.11 Storytelling

Storytelling is one of the oldest tools.^{13,14,15}

Through stories we can share with, relate to, learn from and be inspired by each other.

Storytelling is a tool with which we want to achieve the impact of being relatable and remembered.

Storytelling is a legacy building tool, and we want FEMaLe to have a legacy to which everyone can relate, learn from and draw inspiration.

Let's tell and share our stories, let FEMaLe be an empowering storytelling vessel and let's make it a project that will inspire others. In writing, audio or video - maybe a combination.

How to use storytelling?

Let's tell and share our stories, let FEMaLe be an empowering storytelling vessel and let's make it a project that will inspire others.

Your every action is a story and based on the FEMaLe mindset and values found in Section 1, you can evaluate if your actions align with the story FEMaLe wants to tell.

The choice of medium is yours, be it in writing (paper, parchment or carved in stone) audio or video.

Your stories should be uploaded to a yet to be determined platform that only FEMaLers can access.

When to use storytelling?

All the time and whenever. Seriously. They all help tell the FEMaLe story.

¹³ <https://blog.hubspot.com/marketing/storytelling>

¹⁴ <https://www.i-scoop.eu/using-storytelling-strengthen-brand/>

¹⁵ <https://www.forbes.com/sites/kimberlywhitler/2018/07/14/3-reasons-why-storytelling-should-be-a-priority-for-marketers/?sh=d00f3dc6758e>

4. Let's define the internal dissemination KPIs

Inspired by the concept of '*What gets measured gets managed*', we have defined a single and simple KPI for 9.2. **Before 2022 all FEMaLers must actively use all tools found within this document.** The same KPIs will be measured in 2022, 2023 and 2024.

Through tutorials, workshops and the slew of reasons given for using each tool in this FEMaLe Dissemination Package, we are confident that all FEMaLers, stakeholders and partners alike, will use each tool actively, synergistically and in a Half Double framework co-creation-minded fashion.

Let's discover how we are going to measure and work towards our one KPI.

To achieve that ambitious goal let's continuously measure (once a month during an executive meeting) the following questions on a scale from 1-10:

- How well do stakeholders understand how each tool actively contributes to the realization of FEMaLe's values and vision?
- How well do partners understand how each tool actively contributes to the realization of FEMaLe's values and vision?
- How high is stakeholder usage of each tool?
- How high is stakeholder satisfaction using each tool?
- How high is partner usage of each tool?
- How high is partner satisfaction of each tool?
- How many of the 10 tools do you actively use?

Let's expect a certain resistance from most FEMaLers in the very beginning, but let's also believe that they will come to realize that each tool in our toolbox was chosen on purpose.

WP leaders will determine which tools their teams need to prioritize initially.

We expect each WP leader and their team to have slightly different paths to meet our KPI and let's initially identify where each WP leader and their team is in terms of the bullet points above - and let's then find the right co-creation approach to help each team progress.

5. Let's operationalize internal dissemination

TOOL	HOW TO GET GOING
Visual identity and logo	Web Bay (read more in D9.1)
Miro	<p>Firstly create a Miro account</p> <p>Secondly, after creating your profile, continue with this link to take the beginner's course to learn the basics.</p>
Half Double visuals	In part of the beginner's course mentioned right above this sentence, you will learn how to make 'shapes' that will be the foundation of Half Double visuals
Video communication	<p>Learn about Zoom</p> <p>Learn about Meet</p> <p>Learn about Teams</p>
Doodle	Get started with Doodle
SurveyXact	User manual (link to introduction page)
Posters/infographics/ data visualisation	By contacting EQuIP (Peter Lübben).
Employee Branding	You can read an introduction to Employee Branding on pages 15 and can read further by following the links in footnotes 8, 9 and 10 on the same pages.
Storytelling	You can read an introduction to Storytelling on page 16 and can read further by following the links in footnotes 11, 12 and 13 on the same pages.
Frequent updates	<p>3 levels:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Executive From the executive board to all FEMaLers In PDF form. EQuIP will collect and produce the PDF 2) WP leaders From WP leaders to executive board, templates provided by Web Bay 3) Everyone All FEMaLers to all FEMaLers. Explicit instructions to be created

TOOL	More training	Implementation	Timeline
Visual identity and logo	Responsible: Web Bay	Responsible: Web Bay	Start: June 2021
Miro	Responsible: EQuIP	Responsible: EQuIP	Start: July 2021
Half Double visuals	Responsible: EQuIP	Responsible: EQuIP	Start: July 2021
Video communication	Responsible: Each FEMaLers	Responsible: Each FEMaLer	Start: Ready
Doodle	Responsible: AU	Responsible: AU	Start: August 2021
SurveyXact	Responsible: AU	Responsible: AU	Start: August 2021
Posters/infographics/ data visualisation	Responsible: EQuIP	Responsible: EQuIP and FEMaLe partners in need.	Start: Ready - estimated production time is 2 weeks
Employee Branding	Responsible: EQuIP	Responsible: AU will host files	Start: September EQuIP workshops
Storytelling	Responsible: EQuIP	Responsible: AU will host files	Start: September EQuIP workshops
Frequent updates	Responsible: EQuIP	Responsible: AU will host PDFs	Start: August 2021